

Additional file 2

Figure S1. Chromatographic profile of cellulosomal high-molecular-weight fractions. Gel filtration of supernatant fluids from *B. cellulosolvans* cells grown on two carbon sources: A, cellobiose and B, microcrystalline cellulose. After concentration, the supernatant fluids were loaded onto a Superose 6 Increase gel filtration column. Two major peaks were obtained during the gel filtration process for both substrates. Examination of the peaks revealed two different populations of high-molecular-weight protein complexes that were active on CMC. The column was calibrated using blue dextran and thyroglobulin.